

LORE4GroupRS: Explaining group recommendations supported by a local rule-based approach

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Abstract

The proposed European Union regulations for Artificial Intelligence (AI) has highlighted the necessity and importance of explainable AI as a way for understanding the output and working basis of current AI systems. In the context of recommender systems as popular AI-based tools focused on providing users with the items that best fit their preferences and needs in a search space overloaded with possible choices, the development of explainable recommendation approaches currently has an increasing interest nowadays. However, most of the research efforts are focused on explaining individual recommendations. In contrast, the current contribution is centered on developing a novel approach for generating post-hoc explanations over the output of group recommender systems. To accomplish this goal, it is used the local rule-based explanation approach (LORE), popular in machine learning-based settings. The development of an experimental protocol based on item tags for evaluating the proposed approach in terms of model fidelity and feature coverage rate, points out that it is able to achieve appropriate fidelity values, while covers most of the features used for characterizing items.

Keywords: group recommendation, local rule-based explanation, model fidelity, feature coverage rate

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1 Introduction

The proposed European Union regulations for Artificial Intelligence (the AI Act), has raised the necessity and importance of explainable AI in current AI-based systems [1]. Explainability in AI and machine learning (ML) has been then identified as a relevant goal, because they ensure transparency, trust, and accountability in relation to the final users and the computational system's performance. By understanding how and why AI models make specific predictions or decisions, stakeholders can identify and mitigate biases, improve model accuracy, and also comply with regulatory requirements [2]. In this way, it is boosted the user trust by making complex algorithms more accessible and comprehensible, allowing users to trust the behavior of the system [3].

Across the diverse paradigms of AI-based systems, recommender systems are currently established as popular applications based on their goal of providing users with the information items that best fit their preferences and needs, in a product space overloaded with multiple choice [4]. More recently, group recommender systems [5] have also gained popularity taking into account the existence of scenarios with items that are usually consumed by groups and not individually, such as TV programs, movies, or touristic packages. Two main approaches have been regarded in group recommendation: 1) preference aggregation-based approaches, based on the construction of a pseudo-user profile that represents the group's preference and is used for recommendation delivery, and 2) recommendation aggregation-based approaches, based on the aggregation of the individual recommendations provided for each group member [5].

Due to the relevance of trustworthiness in the recommendation context, in recent years, several research efforts have focused on developing explainability approaches for generated recommendations [3]. Two main groups of approaches have been developed: 1) intrinsic approaches, focused on understanding the operational characteristics of the black-box recommendation model, and 2) post-hoc approaches, focused on explaining the output of the black-box recommendation model, with the support of a second interpretable model [3].

One of the recognized advantages of post hoc recommendation explanation is its ability to be coupled with any black-box recommendation model [3, 6, 7], in contrast to intrinsic explanation approaches which are usually provided as an inherent part of a specific recommendation approach [8], and therefore lack appropriate generalization capabilities.

Nevertheless, most of the previous research efforts both at the individual and group recommendation level, have been centered on intrinsic approaches [3, 8, 9]. Specifically for group recommendation, Quijano-Sanchez et al. [10] present a methodology that provides explanations about the generated group recommendations, which are supported by the social relationships between the group members. Tran Trang et al. [11] explore different types of social choice-based explanations based on the underlying

mechanism of group recommendations generation. Recently, Barile et al. [12] evaluate how the specific distribution of preferences across the group members, determines the most effective social choice-based explainable approach.

In a different direction, the current work is focused on building a post-hoc explanation approach in group recommendation, which is built over the local rule-based explanation method (LORE) [13]. LORE is a well-established framework for explainability in machine learning which stands out in the related literature due to its transparency, intuitiveness, and easy reproducibility, in contrast to other recent explainability approaches in machine learning [14] and recommender systems [15], that are supported by complex architectures which are difficult to calibrate and reproduce.

Specifically, the contributions of the current paper rely on:

- Introducing a novel framework for local rule-based explanations generations in individual and group recommender systems.
- The development and execution of an experimental protocol for evaluating the proposed framework in a recommender systems context.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the LORE4GroupRS framework for generating recommendation explanations for groups, which can be also used for individual recommendation. Section 3 is focused on evaluating the proposal. Section 4 concludes the contribution, pointing out future works.

2 Explaining group recommendations through a local rule-based approach

The objective of our research work is the development of a explainable group recommendation framework, which will be supported by the recommendation aggregation paradigm [5], and the local rule-based explainability approach [13]. It is composed of the following stages: 1) Individual and group recommendation generation, 2) Explanations generation for the individual recommendations, and 3) Explanation generation for groups. In this section it will be explained in detail each of these stages.

2.1 Individual and group recommendation generation

This is usually the initial stage of any group recommendation approach that is supported by the recommendation aggregation paradigm [5].

In the context of the current work, this stage is modeled as the rating prediction task. This task is performed by a rating prediction model M that has been trained using a large dataset of user ratings $R = \{r_{ui}\}$, provided by a set of users $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_n\}$ over some of the items in a set $I = \{i_1, i_2, i_3, \dots, i_n\}$. This rating prediction model is able to calculate the unknown rating $p_{ui} = M(u, i)$, related to some user u about some unknown item i .

Being G the group of users that will receive the final recommendations, in this stage for each group member $u_k \in U$, it is calculated the set of preference values P_{u_k} over the unknown items $i_j \in I$: $P_{u_k} = \{p_{u_k, i}\}$, $\forall_i r_{u_k, i} \notin R$

Subsequently, the set of recommended items for u_k , Rec_{u_k} , is composed of the set of items i which value $p_{u_k,i}$ is equal or over a threshold $pref_{th}$: $Rec_{u_k} = \{i\}, \forall_i p_{u_k,i} \geq pref_{th}$

The individual recommendations generated for each group member are then combined using different aggregation approaches [5], for obtaining the group recommendations.

2.2 Explanations generation for the individual recommendations

As stated previously, this stage will be based on LORE [13], a popular local rule-based explanation approach for tabular data. Being formerly conceived for explaining the output of supervised classification tasks [13], it is needed to be transformed to be used in the recommender systems scenario.

To accomplish this aim, it is necessary to take into account the following definitions:

Definition 1: *Content-based item profile:* A content-based item profile:

$$prof_i = \{(a_k = v_j^{a_k})\}, \forall_{a_k} a_k \in A \quad (1)$$

is represented by a set of attributes A , each attribute a_k characterized by their corresponding value $v_j^{a_k}$. For example, in the case of a movie, this could be a valid profile: $\{director = 'ChristopherNolan', country = 'USA'\}$, being $A = \{director, country\}$. For the context of the current contribution, this profile will be limited to categorical attributes, needing the use of numerical attributes, a further formalization that is out of our current scope.

Definition 2: *Similarity between item profiles:* Here we are interested on using a content-based similarity between user profiles. Therefore, it will be used the Jaccard coefficient [16] for calculating the similarity between two item profiles $prof_{i1}$ and $prof_{i2}$: $sim(prof_{i1}, prof_{i2}) = \frac{|prof_{i1} \cap prof_{i2}|}{|prof_{i1} \cup prof_{i2}|}$

Definition 3: *Individual recommendation explanation:* An individual recommendation explanation e is defined as a pair of objects $e = \langle r, \phi \rangle$. r is a rule with the shape $r = \{(a_k = v_j^{a_k})\} \rightarrow i$, having its antecedent a set of attributes $a_k \in A$, with their respective values (named below as *splitcondition*). The role of such antecedent is to describe the reason for the recommendation of the consequent item i in the antecedent of the rule.

On the other hand, $\phi = \{(a_{k_1} = v_j^{a_{k_1}})\}, \{(a_{k_2} = v_j^{a_{k_2}})\}, \dots\}$, represents a set of counterfactual rules, which are the minimal changes that are necessary to do over the antecedents of the rule r , for becoming the item i into non-recommended, taking into account the attribute-based characterization of those items which ratings predicted in the previous stage 1 where under the $pref_{th}$ threshold.

The goal of this section is therefore, calculating the set of individual recommendation explanations E_i , for each item i in the set of recommended items, $i \in Rec_{u_k}$, suggested to each user u_k , and also across the group G . Particularly, for each recommended item i it will be calculated a set of similar items S_i . Based on the current user

preference over such items' neighborhood, it is calculated the mentioned set of individual recommendation explanations. For each recommended item to each user group, the steps of this procedure are explained in the following subsections:

2.2.1 Item's neighborhood calculation

In this step, it is calculated the set I_i of items that are similar to the recommended item i , considering all the available items in the dataset. In this case this set is composed by all the items which similarity with i is over a similarity threshold sim_{th} :

$$I_i = \{j\}, \forall_j sim(profile_i, profile_j) \geq sim_{th} \quad (2)$$

Based on I_i , it is built a set of instances Z that will be the input for the next step of this stage. Each instance, characterizing each item j in I_i , will be composed of:

1. A set of feature characteristics, represented by all the terms in the profile $prof_j$.
2. A decision $d(j)$ associated to the current item, that could be their recommendation \hat{j} , or not recommendation \hat{j} . It depends on the rating value r_{uj} associated to the corresponding user u over this item, that could be at the training set R , or at the calculated preference values P . If such rating is over the preference threshold $pref_{th}$, the associated decision will be to recommend the item ($d(j) = 1$). Otherwise, it will be to do not recommend the item ($d(j) = 0$)

2.2.2 Extraction of Local rule-based recommendation explanations

For extracting the local rules that will be used for explanations, it is processed the set of instances Z composed of items j which were detected in the neighborhood of the recommended i to be explained. For this set of instances, it is constructed a decision tree built over the qualitative attribute values of the items for composing the branches, and the decision of *recommendation* ($d(j)=1$) or *not recommendation* ($d(j)=0$) for each j as leaves of the tree. This approach has been also taken into account in the former LORE approach [13], and can be performed through basic decision tree induction algorithms such as ID3-like [13].

Once this tree is built, the first component r of the explanation (r, ϕ) associated to the recommended item i , is built by composing a rule which antecedent is the joining of split conditions located at a path of the tree from the root to the leaf, verifying that: 1) the corresponding leaf represents the decision of recommending the item, and 2) all the split conditions in the path are satisfied for the current item i .

Finally, it is necessary to calculate the second component ϕ of the explanation (r, ϕ) , which represents the counterfactuals (i.e. the minimal changes in r for becoming the item i into not recommended ($d(i) = 0$)). With this aim in mind, at first we define a function nf that represented the number of falsified split conditions:

Definition 4: *Number of falsified split conditions* nf : The number of falsified split conditions $nf(s, i)$, represents the amount of split conditions in the set s that are not satisfied by the item i .

Based on Definition 4, the counterfactuals explanations for the item i are obtained through a two-steps procedure: 1) Generate all the paths from the root to the leaves,

which have in the leave the decision of *notrecommendation*, and 2) For all the identified paths, just keep those paths s where the value of $nf(s, i)$ is minimal (e.g. the paths that suggest the minimal necessary transformations for becoming the recommended item i into not recommended).

Algorithm 1 presents a scheme of the steps discussed at this section. At first, Line 1 initializes the sets r and ϕ to store the explanation rules and its counterfactuals. Subsequently, Line 2 obtains the set of similar items I_i to the item i , which associated information is used for building the set of instances Z (Lines 3-5), each one composed by the attribute values of each j , and the decision of recommending or not recommending it. Z is used for building a decision tree c (Line 6) which is used next for constructing the explanation. First, all the paths of the trees are explored, for finding those r that effectively explain the recommendation of the item i , based on its attribute values (Lines 7-13). Finally, the counterfactual explanations ϕ are generated (Lines 14-20), backed by all the paths in the generated tree that lead to the no recommendation decision (Line 15), and keeping only those paths with the minimal difference in relation to the currently recommended item i (Lines 16-20). These paths are retrieved as part of the final recommendation explanation (r, ϕ) (Line 21).

Algorithm 1 Algorithm for obtaining the explanation for the recommended item i

Require: Recommended item i to be explained

Ensure: Explanation (r, ϕ) associated to the recommendation of item i

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1:  $r = \{\}, \phi = \{\}$ 
2:  $I_i = \text{GetNeighbors}(i)$ 
3:  $Z = \{\}$ 
4: for all Item  $j$  in  $I_u$  do
5:    $Z = Z \cup (\text{prof}_j, d(j))$ 
6: end for
7:  $c = \text{BuildTree}(Z)$ 
8: for all Path  $p$  for root to leaves in  $c$  do
9:   verified=true
10:  for all Split condition  $sp$  in path  $p$  do
11:    if  $i$  does not satisfy  $sp$  then
12:      verified=false
13:    end if
14:  end for
15:  if verified=true and decision in the leaf of  $p$  is recommendation then
16:     $r = r \cup sp$ 
17:  end if
18: end for
19:  $min_n = \infty$ 
20: for all Path  $p$  for root to leaves in  $c$ , with decision of norecommendation in the leaf of  $p$  do
21:    $n = nf(p, i)$ 
22:   if  $n < min_n$  then
23:      $\phi = \{\}; \phi = \phi \cup p; min_n = n$ 
24:   end if
25:   if  $n = min_n$  then
26:      $\phi = \phi \cup p$ 
27:   end if
28: end for
29: Retrieve  $E = (r, \phi)$ 

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Fig. 1 Example of decision tree generated with the current approach.

Figure 1 illustrates an example of a tree that would be generated by this algorithm, built using tags as attributes for characterizing items. In this case, the generated explanation (r, ϕ) for some recommended i would be composed of $r = (disney : yes, witch : no, princess : yes) \rightarrow recommend$ and $\phi = (((disney : yes, witch : no, princess : no) \rightarrow donotrecommend), ((disney : yes, witch : yes) \rightarrow donotrecommend))$

2.3 Explanation generation for groups

As the third stage of the current approach, the explanation generation for groups will be performed by merging the individual explanations built for each member of the group in the previous stage. It will be performed through a three-steps approach:

1. Perform the union of all the split conditions at the r components associated to each group member, into a group factual explanation $r_G: r_G = \bigcup_{u \in G} r_u$
2. Being a_k an attribute associated to some split condition in r_G , it is then calculated all a_k that appear more than once in the joined split condition r_G . Subsequently, it is removed all the split conditions having such a_k attributes. (i.e. it guarantees the removal of contradicted split conditions appeared across the joining process, as $a_k = v_1$ and $a_k = v_2$ in the same r_G).
3. Finally, the group-focused explanation is composed by the updated factual explanation r_{G^*} obtained as output of the previous step, and all the counterfactuals obtained for individuals; having the shape $e_G = \{r_{G^*}, \phi_{u_1}, \phi_{u_2}, \dots, \phi_{u_k}\}$, with $u_k \in G$.

3 Experiments

This section develops and executes a compact experimental setting focused on evaluating the current proposal. Herein, Section 4.1 presents the dataset, evaluation metric, and the overall used protocol. Section 4.2 presents and discussed the obtained results.

3.1 Experimental protocol

This section describes the protocol used for evaluating the current proposal.

Dataset: As primary dataset in recommender system research, here it will be used the MovieLens dataset ¹. This dataset contains 100000 rating values and 3600 tag applications over 9000 movies by 600 users. As will be explained below, tags play an essential role in this work, as it will be used for building the user profiles.

Evaluation metrics: The Model Fidelity (MF) has been accepted as an appropriate evaluation metric for characterizing the performance of an explanation approach [6, 7]. It is focused on measuring the proportion of recommended items by an approach M , for which it was possible the generation of a post-hoc explanation, and it is defined as follows: $ModelFidelity(M) = \frac{|recommended\ and\ explainable\ items(M)|}{|recommended\ items(M)|}$.

Additionally, it will be also used the Feature Coverage Ratio (FCR) for measuring the explanation performance [17]. It evaluates how many different attributes are shown in the overall set of generated explanations. Being N_a the number of used attributes and A the overall set of attributes, it would be defined as: $FCR(M) = \frac{N_a}{|A|}$

Evaluation procedure: Using the described dataset and metrics, the evaluation of the proposed approach is performed through the following steps:

1. At first, it is necessary to obtain the item profiles $prof_i$ composed of the attributes that characterized them. In the frame of the used dataset, an item profile will be represented by a binary vector, indicating the presence or absence of each considered tag in the current item i . Specifically, it will be limited to the top m more frequent tags, having then $prof_i$ a dimension m .
2. Afterwards, the available ratings in the dataset is split into training and test sets, using a user-based hold out procedure. This partition just included those items that have been tagged by some of the top m frequent tags identified in the previous step. For the remaining items, it would not be possible the generation of some explanations taking into account that they have not selected any tag associated to them.
3. For all the ratings in the test set, it is generated a new rating prediction using an individual recommendation method. Subsequently, each new prediction greater than the preference threshold $pref_{th}$ is associated with the recommendation of the linked item. For such cases, it is used the methodology presented at the current contribution for explaining the individual recommendations. Model fidelity and the Feature Coverage Ratio are used for evaluating such explanations.
4. Finally, a group formation criteria is used for identifying groups across the users in the rating dataset. Furthermore, using a recommendation aggregation scheme, the rating prediction for such groups are generated. Finally, using the approach presented at Section 2.3 of the current contribution, the group recommendation explanations are generated, using as base the individual explanations obtained in the previous step of this procedure. The mentioned metrics are also used for evaluating such explanations.

In the current setting, it will be used as individual recommendation method the traditional Koren’s SVD recommendation approach [4]. For group composition criteria, it will be ensured that groups will be composed by members that have rated a common

¹<https://grouplens.org/datasets/movielens/>

Table 1 Performance of the approach for the individual recommendation scenario. $m = 40$, $pref_{th} = 3.6$.

sim_{th}	0	0.05	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3
Model Fidelity	0.7483	0.7925	0.7174	0.6755	0.6667	0.6225	0.553
Feature Coverage Ratio	0.725	0.65	0.675	0.525	0.55	0.275	0.175

Table 2 Performance of the approach for the individual recommendation scenario. $m = 40$, $sim_{th} = 0.05$.

$pref_{th}$	3	3.2	3.4	3.6	3.8	4.0	4.2
Model Fidelity	0.8798	0.8783	0.8638	0.7925	0.6622	0.4724	0.2549
Feature Coverage Ratio	0.2	0.45	0.6	0.65	0.775	0.725	0.725

set of items [5]. The rating average will be used as the recommendation aggregation scheme [5]. In addition, groups of size 3 will be considered.

In a different direction, several values will be explored for the following parameters of the presented proposal: 1) m , used for identifying the top m frequent tags used for building the user profiles; 2) the threshold sim_{th} , used for obtaining the neighborhood for the item i to be explained, and that is used for building the decision tree; and 3) the preference threshold $pref_{th}$, used for identifying whether some item should be recommended or not, based on their predicted rating.

Finally, as inner parameter of the tree induction process, it is considered as stopping criteria the threshold $stop_{th} = 0.2$ (i.e. when certain node verifies that $|D_{classA}|/|D| < 0.2$ for some $classA \in \{recommended, notrecommended\}$ being D and D_{classA} their of objects and objects in $classA$ respectively, then the node expansion stops for such stage.

3.2 Results

This section is focused on presenting the results obtained through our evaluation protocol, both for individual and group explanations.

Tables 1-4 present the results associated for the individual explanation generation (i.e. just the first three steps of the evaluation procedure). Specifically, Table 1 presents the performance of the discusses metrics for 40 tags ($m = 40$) and a preference threshold $pref_{th} = 3.6$. Regarding the parameter sim_{th} , used as threshold for selecting the item neighbors that are used for building the decision tree, it is relevant that it is considered the case $sim_{th} = 0$, which means that all the available items are used for building the decision tree (i.e. a global approach). Subsequently, it is regarded $sim_{th} \in [0.05; 0.3]$ with step 0.05.

Overall, it is relevant that the best performance in terms of fidelity was obtained for $sim_{th} = 0.05$, evidencing that the approach focused on building a local explanation tailored to the current item outperforms the use of a global approach using all the data. In a different direction, as could be expected, such global approach reaches the best feature coverage ratio (0.725), but the result associated to $sim_{th} = 0.05$ is also close to such best performance.

Table 3 Performance of the approach for the individual recommendation scenario. $m = 10$, $pref_{th} = 3.6$.

sim_{th}	0	0.05	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3
Model Fidelity	0.7842	0.708	0.708	0.708	0.7118	0.7209	0.7183
Feature Coverage Ratio	0.9	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7

Table 4 Performance of the approach for the individual recommendation scenario. $m = 10$, $sim_{th} = 0.05$.

$pref_{th}$	3	3.2	3.4	3.6	3.8	4.0	4.2
Model Fidelity	0.8052	0.807	0.7922	0.708	0.5956	0.425	0.2008
Feature Coverage Ratio	0.4	0.5	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7

Table 5 Performance of the approach for the group recommendation scenario. $m = 40$, $pref_{th} = 3.6$.

sim_{th}	0	0.05	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3
Model Fidelity	0.2097	0.1129	0.1290	0.08065	0.0483	0.0968	0.0322
Feature Coverage Ratio	0.325	0.2	0.2	0.15	0.125	0.05	0.05

Subsequently, Table 2 presents the results associated to the same experimental setting, but fixing $sim_{th} = 0.05$, and varying $pref_{th} \in [3; 4.2]$ with step 0.2. Being this threshold focused on determining when a rating prediction should lead or not lead to an item recommendation, it is interesting to mention that for the values of 3, 3.2, and 3.4, it is obtained similar fidelity values around 0.87.

For values over 3.6, the performance decreases quickly, suggesting that valuable preferences that should be considered for the explanation generation, are actually discarded. For larger values of $pref_{th}$ it is obtained a better coverage ratio; however such increased number of features do not guarantee the explanation generation of a larger number of items.

Tables 3-4 illustrate the results of a similar experimental configuration, but using a smaller number of tags ($m = 10$). Regarding Table 3 in contrast to the previous case, in this compact scenario the global explanation approach ($sim_{th} = 0$) obtained the best performance. In relation to the feature coverage rate, overall it can be detected a similar behavior that in the case $m = 40$ reaching a lower value for larger sim_{th} . This also applies for Table 4 focused on studying $pref_{th}$, where for $pref_{th} \in [3; 3.4]$ similar fidelity values are obtained, a decreasing in fidelity is reached for larger values, and finally an increasing in the feature coverage ratio is done at such values.

On the other hand, Tables 5-8 are focused on group recommendation and therefore includes the fourth step of our experimental protocol. Taking into account the complexity of the nature of group recommendation, here the results are more difficult to interpret in relation to individual recommendation. Table 5 ($m = 40$, $pref_{th} = 3.6$) and Table 7 ($m = 10$, $pref_{th} = 3.6$) show that the best performance in terms of model fidelity was obtained for the global approach ($sim_{th} = 0$); therefore it makes necessary to screen the reasons for this behavior in the group scenario, in contrast to the individual case where the local explanation ($sim_{th} = 0.05$) performs better. Furthermore,

Table 6 Performance of the approach for the group recommendation scenario. $m = 40$, $sim_{th} = 0$.

$pref_{th}$	3.2	3.4	3.6	3.8	4.0	4.2
Model Fidelity	0.0263	0.1067	0.2097	0.4167	0.5778	0.45
Feature Coverage Ratio	0.025	0.075	0.325	0.475	0.45	0.175

Table 7 Performance of the approach for the group recommendation scenario. $m = 10$, $pref_{th} = 3.6$.

sim_{th}	0	0.05	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3
Model Fidelity	0.2	0.1538	0.1538	0.1538	0.1538	0.1231	0.1231
Feature Coverage Ratio	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.3

Table 8 Performance of the approach for the group recommendation scenario. $m = 10$, $sim_{th} = 0$.

$pref_{th}$	3.2	3.4	3.6	3.8	4.0	4.2
Model Fidelity	0.0684	0.1918	0.2	0.5484	0.46	0.1667
Feature Coverage Ratio	0.2	0.8	0.7	0.9	0.9	0.9

it is interesting to analyze some unexpected results such as the case of $sim_{th} = 0.25$ for Table 5 to identify the nature of the groups that lead to such behavior. Concerning the coverage rate, here it is obtained a behavior that is similar to the individual case.

Finally, the study of $pref_{th}$ shows that the better performance is obtained for values around $pref_{th} = 4$, which is over the values obtained for the individual case. It then suggests that the threshold for considering a group preference as indicator of possible recommendation, would be higher at the group level in relation to the individual case. Overall, the obtained results have demonstrated that the proposed framework is able to generated recommendation explanations with appropriate fidelity values and reaching high feature coverage rates.

4 Conclusions

The current contribution has been focused on bringing the local rule-based explanation approach into the context of group recommender systems. To accomplish this goal, it is developed a methodology that includes individual recommendation generation, item’s neighborhood calculation, extraction of local rule-based recommendation explanations, and the explanation generation for groups. An experimental procedure focused on generating explanations based on item’s tags, shows that the proposal obtains appropriate values of model fidelity and feature coverage rate for both individual and group recommendations. Future works will be focused on exploring different approaches for generating the rules used for explanations [13]. Also, the benchmarking of the current proposal with other explanation paradigms in machine learning, such as LIME and SHAP [3], will be explored.

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